

THE DETERMINATION OF THE INTERACTION TERMS IN STRESS AND STRAIN
BASED QUADRATIC POLYNOMIAL FAILURE CRITERIA .

A.M. Roach and K.E.Evans

Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Liverpool,
P.O.Box 147,
Liverpool, L69 3BX, UK

ABSTRACT

A strain based quadratic failure criterion has certain practical advantages over the more conventional stress based criteria. In both cases acceptance of such criteria is limited by the difficulty of accurately measuring the interaction term. In this paper a new experimental method has been used to obtain this interaction term from a uniaxial test specimen. Finite element analysis has been used to aid in specifying the specimen geometry. The method has been shown to produce a reasonable value for the interaction term. A comparison of the different methods produces a way of determining the accuracy and reliability of the predicted failure envelope.

KEYWORDS Failure Criterion, Finite Element Analysis, Biaxial, Tensile,
Test Method.

1. INTRODUCTION

A number of phenomenological criteria for predicting the strength of anisotropic fibre reinforced composites have been developed, the majority of which have been derived in stress space. In particular, the Tsai-Hill criterion (1) and the stress tensor polynomial failure criterion suggested by Tsai and Wu (2) have received widespread attention. The Tsai-Hill criterion has the advantage of its operational simplicity. However, it neglects the differences of strength in tension and compression. The Tsai-Wu criterion gives a more general description of failure. However, the difficulties encountered in measuring the interaction strength term (F_{ij} $i \neq j$) from biaxial stress tests (3) have hindered its widespread use.

In view of the advantages of measuring strain to failure rather than stress, a phenomenological polynomial failure criterion in strain space has been proposed (4).

A new test method (5) to obtain a biaxial stress state from a uniaxial strain test is considered. This test can be used to determine the interaction strength term of the stress based quadratic

criteria and the non-interaction terms in the strain based criterion. It has been shown that only one set of tests is needed to completely characterise both criteria. (6)

In this paper we present results from tensile tests on glass fibre epoxy and carbon fibre epoxy and apply stress and strain based failure criteria. Values using the new test method are compared with values obtained from conventional off-axis tests.

2. UNIAXIAL STRAIN TESTS

To obtain a biaxial stress state from a uniaxial strain test a new test has been developed that achieves this aim by preventing transverse Poisson contraction under tensile loading. This is done by the imposition of a zero boundary condition transverse to the loading direction. Figure 1 shows schematically the test method.

The biaxial stress fields are found with the aid of the generalised Hookean (7) law applied to an orthotropic composite. For a longitudinal strain test, the biaxial stress field is

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{E_{22} \nu_{12}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1^* \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

E_{11} and E_{22} are the Young's moduli in the longitudinal and transverse fibre orientations, ν_{12} , ν_{21} , the major and minor Poisson's ratios in the 1-2 plane and ϵ_1^* the longitudinal failure strain in the test shown in Figure 1.

If the transverse strain does not equal zero then the stress field is written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{11} \nu_{12}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{E_{22} \nu_{12}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1^+ \\ \epsilon_2^+ \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

If it is assumed that the uniaxial strain tests are linear up to failure, then the failure strain ϵ_1^* can be expressed in terms of stress

$$\epsilon_1^* = \left(\frac{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}}{E_{11}} \right) \sigma_1^\Delta \quad (3)$$

where σ_1^Δ is the stress measured at the failure strain ϵ_1^* . In general, this is different from σ_1^* and σ_2^* .

For the sake of simplicity, the case for planar orthotropic materials in the 1-2 plane is considered. Neglecting the out of plane stress, the Tsai-Hill criterion can be expressed as

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_1^*}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{\sigma_1^{*2}}\right) - \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_2^*}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

σ_1^* and σ_2^* are the material longitudinal and transverse failure strengths, σ_1 and σ_2 are the components of longitudinal and transverse stress in an off-axis test.

The term $1/\sigma_1^{*2}$ is included in equation (3) to account for the interaction between stress components. The criterion is re-written, with the term L_{12} as the interaction term, as

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_1^*}\right)^2 - L_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_2^*}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

The stress conditions of the zero strain test have been substituted into (4) to give an expression for L_{12} .

$$L_{12} = \frac{1}{E_{11}E_{22}\nu_{12}} \left[\left(\frac{E_{11}}{\sigma_1^*}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{E_{22}\nu_{12}}{\sigma_2^*}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{\epsilon_1^*}\right)^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

If σ_1 is measured at the failure strain ϵ_1^* then using equation (2) L_{12} can be calculated in terms of stress.

$$L_{12} = \frac{1}{E_{11}E_{22}\nu_{12}} \left[\left(\frac{E_{11}}{\sigma_1^*}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{E_{22}\nu_{12}}{\sigma_2^*}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{E_{11}}{\sigma_1}\right)^2 \right] \quad (7)$$

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

It is possible to approach the ideal case of zero transverse strain by reducing the specimen aspect ratio. Finite element analysis has been used to aid specimen design.

The elements used were eight noded solid block elements in three dimensions. Due to symmetry considerations it was only necessary to model a quarter of the specimen. Firstly, a standard tensile coupon having an aspect ratio of six was modelled. It was found that the theoretical transverse strain was comparable with that measured experimentally in a standard specimen, which has the same aspect ratio, which suggested that the normal assumption of boundary symmetry conditions was correct.

Further geometries were modelled having progressively smaller aspect ratios. The aspect ratio was changed by keeping the width constant whilst changing the specimen length. It was found that a reduction in aspect ratio was accompanied by a reduction in transverse strain.

In each case, the same longitudinal strain was imposed. The value chosen was well below the failure strain (13.0×10^{-3} in the case of Glass-Epoxy and 4.0×10^{-3} for Carbon-Epoxy). The theoretical transverse strain is compared with the experimental value at the same longitudinal strain in figures 2 and 3.

Originally there was some worry that the reduction in gauge length would result in stress concentrations imposed by the grips affecting a large part of the gauge length. Stress contour plots for both materials for specimens having the shortest gauge length selected have shown

that even the shortest gauge length has a uniform stress field over most of its area. From finite element analysis, stress concentrations imposed by the grips are not considered to be the cause of failure and this was borne out experimentally.

4. EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used in this study were glass epoxy HYE 9082AF supplied by Fiberite Ltd. and carbon epoxy 914- TS -5-34 supplied by Ciba Geigy Ltd. Both materials were uni - directional pre preg tape.

The material properties were determined according to BS 2782 part 10 method 3 and are shown in Table 1. The specimens were gauged using linear strain gauges. The interaction term in the conventional Tsai - Hill criterion is considered to be $1/\sigma_1^{*2}$. A value for the interaction term can, therefore, be calculated from standard longitudinal tests.

Off - axis tests have been carried out on both materials. In accordance with other workers, (8) (9) the aspect ratio chosen was fifteen and the end tabs were of the same material and fibre orientation as the specimen. Two longitudinal gauges, one on either side, were attached to the middle of the specimen. Two more longitudinal gauges were attached two centimetres from the end tab. Both sets of strain gauges recorded the same value of strain. This implied that there were no bending effects and that a uniform stress/strain field existed in the specimens. Off - axis tests have previously been used to determine interaction strength terms. Values of off - axis angle can be substituted into equation (5) to obtain a value for L_{12} . This should be the same regardless of the angle chosen. The results for the off - axis tests and the corresponding L_{12} s for glass epoxy are shown in table 4 and those for carbon epoxy in table 5.

The reduced aspect ratio tests were carried out in the longitudinal fibre direction. The specimen width was kept constant at seventy millimetres and the aspect ratio changed by varying the gauge length. Due to the practical considerations of attaching strain gauges , it was not possible to test specimens having an aspect ratio less than 0.2 with the tensile testing machine grip width available. The aspect ratios tested were 0.75, 0.5 and 0.3 for glass epoxy and 0.5 and 0.3 for carbon epoxy. The stresses and strains at failure were recorded.

5. RESULTS

It was found that although the transverse strain at failure reduced with aspect ratio, the longitudinal failure stress remained unchanged. Table 2 shows the results for glass epoxy and Table 3 for carbon epoxy. The theoretical longitudinal failure stress was calculated from equation (2) thus

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{E_{11}}{1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}} (\epsilon_1^+ + \nu_{21} \epsilon_2^+) \quad (8)$$

In both cases, the failure stress was below the longitudinal failure stress σ_1^* and above σ_2^* . In general good agreement was found between the calculated and measured values of failure stress. The mechanism of failure was a combination of transverse tensile and shear failure in the matrix. Since the failure stress remains constant with varying aspect ratio, it is reasonable to assume that it does so when $\epsilon_1^+ = \epsilon_1^*$. σ_1^A is taken as the average failure stress from the reduced aspect ratio tests. σ_1^- is then substituted into equation (7) to give a value for L_{12} . From equation (8) it can be seen that if σ_1^A is a constant then $\epsilon_1^+ + \nu_{21} \epsilon_2^+$ is also

expected to be a constant. This is shown in Tables 2 and 3. Although the transverse strain was not zero it is possible to extrapolate a linear plot of $1/\epsilon_1^+$ against $-\epsilon_1^+/\epsilon_2^+$ to obtain a value for ϵ_1^* and hence, L_{12} can be calculated from equation 6. This is shown in figure 4 for glass epoxy and figure 5 for carbon epoxy.

6. DISCUSSION

Finite element analysis was used to aid specimen design. It was hoped that it would give an indication of the aspect ratios which it would be suitable to test. Although Figures 2 and 3 show that the error between the predicted values and experimental results increases with decreasing aspect ratio, the general trend is the same. The finite element analysis results suggested that a critical aspect ratio of about 0.3 existed below which the transverse strain was effectively zero. Experimentally, such a cut-off has not been found, although it is more nearly approached for the carbon specimens. This would indicate the possibility of non-elastic effects. However, the comparison of measured stress and strains at failure, using equation (8) implies that the material is effectively elastic right up to failure. The difference between the predicted values and those measured experimentally may be due to the fact that the non-displacement boundary condition can never be as rigidly enforced in a practical situation.

The longitudinal stress at failure does not change with decreasing aspect ratio. The value is different from both σ_1^* and σ_2^* and so lies in a different position on the failure envelope. It is highly likely that a biaxial stress state is achieved using this test method. The experimental failure stress gave good agreement with the calculated value. Since the failure stress remains constant for the aspect ratios tested, it was assumed that this is the case at ϵ_1^* .

The assumption that there is a linear relationship between $-\epsilon_2^+/\epsilon_1^+$ and $1/\epsilon_1^+$ is borne out experimentally in the region tested. Therefore, it is reasonable to extrapolate a plot of $1/\epsilon_1^+$ against $-\epsilon_1^+/\epsilon_2^+$ to obtain a value for ϵ_1^* .

This paper has identified four different methods of determining the interaction term in the Tsai - Hill criterion

- 1) Conventional Tsai -Hill criterion $1/\sigma_1^{*2}$ (equation 4)
- 2) Off - axis tests (equation 5)
- 3) Longitudinal failure strain from uniaxial strain test ϵ_1^* (equation 6)
- 4) Failure stress from uniaxial strain test (equation 7)

Values obtained from methods 1,3,and 4 and an average value from method 2 are shown in Table 6.

The interaction term is a material property and should be the same using different methods. However, it has been revealed that different values are obtained. The differences in the case of method 2 may be due to errors in measuring off - axis angle. The average value is shown in Table 6.

Methods 3 and 4 gave close agreement and was best for carbon epoxy.

The previous assumption using method 1 does not give good agreement with the other methods. The conventional Tsai - Hill value is seen not to produce a good description of failure. The other three values are much closer. Thus, the method is capable of producing a reasonable value for L_{12} .

Further work will be carried out to determine which value of L_{12} gives the most reliable predictions of strength.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A reduction in aspect ratio gives a reduction in transverse strain. The stress at failure for these specimens remains constant. The material remains elastic up to failure. A uniaxial test specimen of low aspect ratio has been shown to give reasonable values for L_{12} . Four different methods can be used to measure the interaction strength term. Differences in the values of L_{12} may give an indication of the validity of using such strength criteria. Further work is needed to determine which method gives the best prediction of strength.

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Figure 1 Schematic Diagram of a Uniaxial Strain Test

Figure 2 Transverse Strain vs. Aspect Ratio for a Longitudinal Strain of 13000×10^{-6} , Glass Epoxy

Figure 3 Transverse Strain vs. Aspect Ratio for a Longitudinal Strain of 4000×10^{-6} , Carbon Epoxy

Figure 4 Plot of $1/\epsilon_1^+$ against $-\epsilon_1^+/\epsilon_2^+$, Glass Epoxy

Figure 5 Plot of $1/\varepsilon_1^+$ against $-\varepsilon_1^+/\varepsilon_2^+$, Carbon Epoxy

TABLE 1 Material Properties

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	σ_1^* (MPa)	σ_2^* (MPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{21}
Glass Epoxy	41.22	10.73	1106	39.69	0.295	0.053
Carbon Epoxy	127.5	9.66	1335	13.91	0.302	0.009

TABLE 2 Results from Reduced Aspect Ratio Tests for Glass Epoxy

$\varepsilon_1^+ \times 10e-6$	$\varepsilon_2^+ \times 10e-6$	σ_{1exp} (MPa)	σ_1 theor	$\varepsilon_1^+ + \nu_{21} \varepsilon_2^+$	Aspect Ratio
-5490	20300	770	838	20.00×10^{-3}	0.76
-5481	20367	779	841	20.07×10^{-3}	0.79
-5420	20619	818	851	20.32×10^{-3}	0.73
-5138	20551	770	862	20.27×10^{-3}	0.31
-5120	20563	850	849	20.28×10^{-3}	0.75
-4870	20636	782	853	20.37×10^{-3}	0.52
-4586	20847	800	862	20.59×10^{-3}	0.51
-4584	20987	775	869	20.74×10^{-3}	0.52
-4550	19916	818	824	19.67×10^{-3}	0.53
-3827	21517	785	894	21.11×10^{-3}	0.32

TABLE 3 Results from Reduced Aspect Ratio Tests for Carbon Epoxy

$\epsilon_1^+ \times 10e-6$	$\epsilon_2^+ \times 10 e-6$	$\sigma_{1exp}(MPa)$	σ_1 theor	$\epsilon_1^+ + \nu_{21} \epsilon_2^+$	Aspect Ratio
-2383	10647	1176	1270	9.93x10-3	0.51
-2209	10637	1300	1275	9.97x10-3	0.511
-2242	10556	1202	1263	9.98x10-3	0.52
-1306	10622	1292	1308	10.23x10-3	0.30
-1242	10599	1318	1312	10.22x10-3	0.30
-1224	10707	1212	1322	10.34x10-3	0.31
-1160	10831	1310	1383	10.82x10-3	0.32
-1135	10815	1322	1382	10.81x10-3	0.30

TABLE 4 Results from Off - Axis Tests on Glass Epoxy

Angle (degrees)	σ (MPa)	$L_{12} \times 10-16$
15.62	232	-2.16
16.23	238	-1.82
16.44	240	-1.72
16.54	245	-1.59
16.87	245	-1.49
16.91	229	-1.78

TABLE 5 Results from Off - Axis Tests on Carbon Epoxy

Angle (degrees)	σ (MPa)	$L_{12} \times 10-16$
21.62	186	5.69
21.75	172	5.41
22.39	154	5.41
23.12	155	6.26
30.57	81	10.10
31.43	83	12.00
31.63	72	9.95
31.73	66	8.30

TABLE 6 Comparison of the Interaction Terms

	Method 1	Method 2	Method 3	Method 4
Glass Epoxy	8.18x10-19	-1.76x10-16	4.61x10-17	3.84x10-16
Carbon Epoxy	5.61x10-19	7.89x10-16	1.21x10-16	1.18x10-16